

UNDERSTANDING THE ROLE OF THE DIASPORIC NETWORK, REMITTANCE AND PHILANTHROPIC CONTRIBUTION IN DEVELOPMENT PROCESS OF GANDHINAGAR AND KACHCHH DISTRICTS OF GUJARAT

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Abstract

The Indian diaspora is one of the largest and prolific communities in the world and the Gujarati diaspora is one of the oldest and the largest Indian diaspora community. The study of Gujarati migration and its diaspora is extremely important to understand the developmental process of Gujarat. Gujarat, lauded as one of the most developed states in India has not reached the position without support from its diaspora, the state has harnessed the help of its Diaspora community abroad. Over the centuries of migration and trade that the Gujarati communities were a part of and after decades of migration to countries like U.S.A, U.K, Canada, Australia, Middle- Eastern and African countries etc., the Gujarati Diaspora community has established itself as a strong force in various social, economic and political spheres. The Gujarati diaspora has strong cultural ties to their homeland and as a result of it, they have a long tradition of philanthropy and aiding in the development of their home and community. The Gujarati diaspora feels a strong sense of duty towards their home and community, and they contribute in various ways in improving and developing their homeland and community. They do so across various spheres like education, healthcare, helping the elderly and many more through the remittances and philanthropy. This flow of remittances to their home villages and towns help in their

development. The government of Gujarat also has recognized their contributions and made schemes that involve the Gujarati Diaspora in the development of the state. It is important to study the complex relationship between the diaspora and the homeland to understand development, philanthropy, the diasporic network and also the future of diaspora engagement. Thus, the paper has analysed the history and patterns of Gujarati migration and the contribution of Gujarati Diaspora to the development of the selected districts for study, namely- Kachchh and Gandhinagar. The paper along with the present positives has also explored the future of the Gujarati Diaspora's contribution in the development of Gujarat and its engagement with its homeland. The paper has attempted to emphasize the need for further governmental policies and intervention in engaging the Gujarati diaspora. To do so, the research paper uses qualitative methods like literary analysis to study the history and pattern of migration, case studies and interviews from the selected districts of Kachchh and Gandhinagar. Some of the villages like Madhapar, Sukhpar and others from Kachchh and Nardipur, Dhamasana and others from Gandhinagar were the selected villages to study the contribution of the Gujarati Diaspora in the development process of Gujarat.

Keywords- *Diaspora, Migration, Remittances, Philanthropy, Development, Case Study*

Introduction

The contributions of Gujarati diaspora populations, notably through mechanisms like remittances and philanthropic donations, have had a considerable impact on the development of places such as Gandhinagar and Kachchh. Gujarat, a state noted for its entrepreneurial spirit and strong global diaspora, provides a unique case study for learning how transnational networks influence local economic and social growth. The Gujarati diaspora is one of the major contributors to the inflow of remittances to India. Remittances are not only used to fund household consumption but also contribute to social development programs such as healthcare, education, disaster relief, and rural infrastructure. The Gujarati diaspora has strong bonds within community in both homeland and abroad across the world. The diasporic network's function in these places is more than just financial support; it also includes the mobilization of human capital, knowledge, and skills. Through different activities, members of the diaspora support technology transfer, promote entrepreneurship, and contribute knowledge that benefits the local workforce. Furthermore, charitable acts by the diaspora have frequently supplemented government programs, resulting in collaborations that fulfil both current needs and long-term development objectives.

Thus, it is important to study the relationship between the Gujarati diaspora and their homeland, and the different facets of it. To do so, the paper has explored two districts of Gujarat- Kachchh and Gandhinagar. The communities of Gandhinagar, the state capital, and Kachchh, a district with a rich cultural legacy and a high risk of natural catastrophes, have

significant relationships to migrants residing abroad, notably in the United States, the United Kingdom, and the Middle East.

The Gujarati Migration- History, Cultural Ties, and Philanthropy

The history of Gujarati diaspora can be traced back to the British Empire of 1870s when the British transported more than one million Indian indentured labourers to countries like Uganda, Kenya, Tanzania, and so on. They were workers working on contract for five or more years in railways, plantations, and infrastructure projects. In 1917, when the indenture system was abolished, most of these workers returned to India, some settled in East Africa and the Caribbean. In the later years of British colonial rule, India experienced frequent conflicts, widespread poverty, famines, and political instability, which prompted many Indians to migrate to East Africa in search for better economic opportunities.

Indians in Uganda faced a difficult period during 1970s under the rule of Idi Amin, he expelled thousands of Indian as part of his policies relating to 'Africanisation.' Indians were forced to leave their properties and businesses behind leading to them migrating to different parts of the world. During this period, many of these families migrated to the UK instead of migrating back to India.

In general, international migration from Gujarat has been beneficial in terms of remittances and bringing in investment. Gujarati diaspora has been a significant factor on the socio-economic, political and cultural milieu of communities in both origin and destination locations (Dhak and Shah, 2011).

According to Ruby Maloni (2019) Gujarat was concentric to the world of the early modern Indian Ocean. Long-distance commercial methods were fine-tuned throughout the sixteenth and seventeenth century. The Indo-Portuguese commerce network prospered in Southeast Asia, followed by the English and Dutch which formed equilibrium between European and Asian traders. Cotton textiles from Gujarat were used to facilitate profitable commerce in pepper and spices in the eastern archipelago.

Many believe that the Gujarati diaspora and development are intricately linked, with substantial developmental disparities within the community (Mehta, 2006). These disparities are exacerbated by the development programmes' building and contestation of a Gujarati-Hindu ethno-religious identity (Sud, 2007). The emergence of sub-nationalism in India, notably in the 'Vibrant Gujarat,' has also influenced the development of the Gujarati diaspora over the years (Bobbio in Kaur and Wahlberg, 2012). Despite these obstacles, the diaspora has demonstrated resilience and, most notably in the instance of Gujarati Hindu immigrant women

in Natal, South Africa, who faced challenges in the socio-economic aspect and dealt with issues of belonging and identity in the diaspora, and subsequently, negotiated new positions within the home (Hiralal, 2013).

Migrants and Diasporic Remittances & Philanthropic contribution:

Diaspora philanthropy is a factor of the development process as it is viewed as a sort of resource transfer from migrants to their home countries. Household remittances, defined as the transfer of money and products from migrants to their family members at home, are a significant component of such resource transfers (Kapur 2004). Remittances and diaspora philanthropy are critical components of the transnational connections that migrant populations retain with their places of origin (Elden 2005; Gupta and Ferguson 1997; Malkki 1994). According to the existing literature, Gujarati diaspora indulges more in social remittances in the form of charity, gifts, and relief during disasters.

Gujarat receives substantial economic remittances, as the Gujarati diaspora is renowned for its charitable nature and its strong transnational connections across the globe. For instance, numerous hospitals, schools, and communities, such as those of the Kuchchi Lewa Patels, are well-organized and support one another. A notable example is the K.K. Super Speciality Hospital, which was constructed on land donated by Gujaratis residing in Africa. In addition, they have contributed crores of rupees to ensure the availability of comprehensive facilities at the hospital. Another example is the Nardipur village in Gandhinagar district, where the diaspora community has contributed to the all-around development of the village. There are many projects they have funded in various ways- from the Panchayat office, village health clinic, village schools, a public park, and numerous temples having contributed money extensively over the years.

Non-resident Gujaratis (NRGs) maintain a strong relation with their country of origin. They have consistently nurtured close ties with relatives, friends, and other individuals in their homeland and across the globe. This bond has only strengthened with the advancement of communication technologies and linkages. With greater access to the internet, NRGs have expanded their connections from social to economic domains. Their engagement is not limited to social activities such as maintaining kinship networks, sending remittances, and participating in religious and social practices, but also includes active interest in various forms of investment. Additionally, another form of linkage is evident through institutional connections, both between the diaspora and the homeland, as well as transnationally. It is through these associational connections, this diasporic community actively participates in various

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philanthropic and social service initiatives, for example, contributing during the devastating earthquake of January 2001, NRGs from around the world united to assist in the recovery and reconstruction of the region's economy and infrastructure helping people who were affected. They mobilized funds from both individuals and organizations, with numerous groups offering support in the form of both human resources and material aid (Dhak and Shah, 2011).

Data Sources, Methods and Methodologies: The paper has analysed the relation between Diaspora and development through the example of Gujarati diaspora and its impact on the development process through the study of two districts of Gujarat namely- Kachchh and Gandhinagar. It has aimed to do so through the means of conducting interviews and case studies in the selected districts of Gujarat. It employs qualitative analysis by analysing the available literature and case studies and interviews from the field. Data was collected through conducting field work, interviews and case studies.

The Case Study of Nardipur village in Gandhinagar District: An Analysis

Nardipur village, located in Gandhinagar district, highlights several tangible examples of how diaspora communities contribute to the socio-economic development of their native regions. The majority of the migrant population from Nardipur has settled in the United States, forming a very prosperous diaspora community. This economic success is visibly reflected in the village's well-maintained infrastructure, including religious institutions, community buildings, and healthcare facilities. The majority of the village has migrated and has seen decades of migration leading to a successful diaspora community that actively contributes to the development of the village.

Interview with village Sarpanch:

As soon as one enters the Nardipur village, they are greeted by the Gram Panchayat, the bus stand and a sitting area for the locals to gather. There, the field investigators interviewed the Sarpanch (Male, Age 50s). He said that most of the households had migrated to foreign countries. And originally, a lot of the migration that took place was done through the regular forms but few cases were observed/informed of illegal migration. The pattern of outmigration continues to this day.

“Most of the youngsters to migrate to USA, Canada, and Australia etc..

More than half the homes among the Patels are vacant in the village.”

(Sarpanch, a male in his 50s).

The migration is further facilitated through the American laws that allow for family blood relatives to also migrate with the family (especially in countries like USA and earlier in

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UK). Gujarati migrants majorly establish their own businesses like liquor stores, grocery stores etc.

Picture: 1 Nardipur Gram Panchayat

The key informant also informed us that the diaspora has been instrumental in the development of the village. They have helped through their remittances and philanthropy to build the village bus stand, the Gram Panchayat office, a new public park, and many temples, like the new Ram Mandir that was being built and has received more than 1 Crore in donations.

Picture:2 Nardipur Bus Stand

Building of Temples in Nardipur: There were numerous beautiful and well-built temples in Nardipur like the Swaminarayan Temple, the Radha Krishna Temple and the new temple that was still under construction, the Ram Temple. All of these temples were built over the years and the diaspora community actively donated to their building.

Picture 2 and 4 The New Ram Temple and The Swaminarayan Temple, Nardipur

An example of their active philanthropy in building temples in Nardipur was through the example of the Ram Temple that was being constructed. It was a wonder in marble with elaborate carvings and intricate craftsmanship. The field investigators were informed by numerous respondents that the cost of constructing the temple was about 4-5 Crores and that a lot of money to build it was donated by the diaspora. This shows that the diaspora is deeply connected to its village, community and culture. The religious ties in the Gujarati diaspora community remain strong and that they actively participate in the building of new temples.

Community Health Centre at Nardipur village, Gandhinagar

One significant example of diaspora contribution is the community health centre near the village's main entrance. During an interview with a medical professional working at the centre, it was revealed that the health facility was originally built in 1964 through donations from migrant families. Over the years, the centre, which began as a primary health facility, was upgraded to a full-fledged community health centre with government assistance. The land for the health centre was donated by migrant families, illustrating how the economic success of the diaspora has translated into tangible community assets.

The Patel community has a significant ageing population, where the younger generation has largely migrated abroad. The health center serves as a critical resource for the village's elderly, as well as for other vulnerable sections of the population. It provides healthcare services either free of charge or at significantly reduced costs, which has proven invaluable for the economically disadvantaged.

Figure 5 Interview with a Medical Professional in Nardipur

The case of Nardipur underscores the critical role that diasporic communities play in fostering local development, not only through financial contributions but also by ensuring sustainable and inclusive growth that benefits all residents, regardless of their socio-economic status. The centre's existence and operation provide a model of how diaspora-driven initiatives, when combined with local and governmental support, can lead to long-term improvements in rural healthcare.

Case Study of Dhamasana Village, Gandhinagar

Dhamasana is a small village that is located in the Gandhinagar district of Gujarat. The migration from Dhamasana is more recent as compared to Nardipur. The village is a village of Leva Patels and most of the migration took place after the 1990s and early 2000s. The migration from this village is to mostly Australia and Canada. There is only some migration to USA and to other countries. As a result, the diaspora is an emerging and new diaspora and this can be seen in the ways in which the diaspora contributes in the development of the village.

Picture 6: One of the Temples in Dhamasana

Interview with one of the seniors in the Village

The key respondent is one of the leaders and elders of the village. He told the interviewers that that the village has seen an increase in migration only in the last couple of decades. Most of the migration that took place earlier happened through marriages and then more and more youngsters wanted to move abroad. According to him, there is also a certain pressure for the youth to move abroad because most of the youth from the Leva Patidar community have migrated to foreign countries.

Picture 7 One of the recently developed housing societies in Dhamasana with many NRI houses

He also said that “more than 60% of households have at least one migrant in their family and many more are migrating, and twenty more have migrated or are going to migrate in 2024 alone.” (Key respondent, male in his 60s) Most of the migration takes place to Australia and Canada and some to USA and other countries.

When asked about philanthropy, he replied that the diaspora donates to the building of temples and to the organization of the Navratri Garba festival in the village. The diaspora from Dhamasana is still stabling itself in the foreign lands, and so the focus for now is own contributing and helping their own families and personal philanthropy.

Thus, in the case of both Nardipur and Dhamasana, the diaspora helps in the development of their home villages but in their own capacities. The diaspora is very important in the development of these villages and their strong familial and cultural bonds, their diasporic networks, help in the process of development of Gujarat.

Case Study on Sukhpar village Earthquake Hospital, Kachchh District:

During the field visit to Sukhpar village in Kutch, the field investigators had the opportunity to engage with Krita Nitin Parmar, a dedicated nurse at the earthquake relief trust hospital. This facility was established in 2002 in response to the catastrophic earthquake that struck Bhuj. It was funded through the collective efforts of migrants from the United Kingdom who raised the necessary financial resources to purchase land and equip the hospital with essential medical supplies.

Picture 8 Interview with Key Respondent

The Key respondent, a nurse, emphasized the hospital's critical role in the local healthcare, as it provides a wide array of medical services at minimal charges. This pricing strategy is deliberately designed to ensure that healthcare is accessible to all segments of the community, regardless of their economic status. As the primary healthcare provider in the region, the hospital addresses not only routine medical needs but also emergencies, thereby fulfilling a vital function in promoting public health and well-being.

Picture 9 The *Sukhpar* Earthquake Hospital

Moreover, the establishment of this hospital illustrates the significance of community involvement in healthcare development, particularly in rural settings. The collaborative efforts of the diasporic community demonstrate how global connections can lead to tangible improvements in local healthcare systems. By facilitating access to medical services, the hospital not only aids in immediate health concerns but also contributes to the overall resilience of the community in the face of future adversities. Thus, the institution stands as a testament to the power of solidarity and collective action in enhancing healthcare access in rural areas and how the Gujarati diaspora played an important role in the development and safety of its homeland.

Case Study on Apna Ghar, Madhapar Village, Kachchh District:

The concept of old age homes has grown in importance in recent years due to societal changes, including nuclear family setups and the migration of younger generations for better opportunities. Apna Ghar located in Madhapar, Kutch, Gujarat, and stands out as home for lost senior citizen seeking care, support, and companionship in their golden years.

Picture: 10 Apna Ghar, an old age home in Madhapar

Apna Ghar was established in 1984 and houses a mixed population of men and women, including approximately 30 senior citizens. It was created to serve elderly individuals who have no next of kin or whose children live abroad. Apna Ghar has become a symbol of the belief that "Service to Humanity is Service to God." The property originally belonged to the

Vekheriya family, who donated it for charitable purposes. Currently, Apna Ghar is managed and supported by contributions from the globally connected diaspora, notably the Shree Kacchi Lewa Patel community.

A small healthcare centre has been built within the premise. A dedicated healthcare facility with visiting doctors and trained nurses ensures that residents' medical needs are promptly addressed. Regular health check-ups and wellness programs are conducted to maintain residents' overall health.

Mrs. Patel, an 84-year-old widow, moved to Apna Ghar after her children relocated abroad. Initially hesitant, she quickly adapted to the welcoming environment. She found companionship among residents with similar life experiences.

Apna Ghar is a prime example of how collaboration and combined efforts by the diaspora community can lead to improved facilities in rural villages like Madhapar. The diasporic networks are important in developing places and how it can lead to a change for the better for many.

The Key Informant, 49- year-old women of Gujarati origin, a second-generation diaspora, is now a Kenyan citizen. However, her heart remains deeply connected to her ancestral village, Madhapar in Kutch, Gujarat. Her mother holds a British Passport but returned to India in her old age to spend her later years in her native place. Every year, she visits her homeland, seeking ways to contribute to and stay connected with her roots. The informant is associated with the Kachchhi Leva Patel Samaj, an organization representing 24 gaon (villages). This samaj is part of a larger, globally recognized community of Kachchhi Leva Patel and is affiliated with BAPS Swami Narayan temple. *According to the informant,*

“Most weddings, community functions in Kenya are celebrated collectively by members of all 24 villages, fostering a sense of unity and shared culture. The society also helps others from their community migrate and adjust in Kenya and in different countries across the world.” (Key Informant, diaspora from Madhapar, age 49)

The informant's father, known for his philanthropic spirit, donated the entire property to support charitable work, specifically for the care of elderly people, now called 'Apna Ghar'.

Interview with PNB Madhapar Branch Manager, Kachchh

There is at least one branch of most of the renowned banks in Madhapar boasting of offering NRI services. Madhapar village is also known as the 'richest village in Asia' because it receives large amount of remittances and has a large diaspora population.

Figure 11 PNB Bank branch, Madhapar

A detailed interview was conducted with the Branch Head of the Punjab National Bank. He told the interviewers that the trend was that the older generation would come back to the village after retirement. It was also observed that many of the older generation returned to India for most of the time or at least of 6 months of the year. This was slowly changing as the next generations that have been born outside India did not want to come back to their village.

The branch manager informed that the bank receives a lot of money in NRI accounts, at present there was around 500 Crore in investments. The economy and development of Madhapar village mostly depended on NRI remittances, but according to him the trend was changing as the younger generation of diaspora do not feel the same connection to India and their village as the older generation and thus, remittances from countries like UK were reducing. According to him, most of the remittances that were sent to Madhapar were from African countries as they still thought of it as a volatile place to live in comparison to UK or USA.

M.S.V. High School, Madhapar, Kachchh

M.S.V High School is located in the central area of Madhapar, where over 800 students are currently enrolled. Founded in 1962, it is a privately aided institution that receives significant donations from the diaspora to support its infrastructural and technological advancements. In an interview with the Principal of M.S.V High school in Madhapar, he informed that the Gujarati diaspora regularly donates to the school for its renovations and sponsors education of deserving in-need students. The diasporic community also sponsors the education of underprivileged students, assisting them with tuition fees and other essential needs. Despite its location in the rural region of Kutch, the school provides a wide range of facilities, including sports and cultural activities. During the conversations with members of the diasporic community, who were visiting the town for holidays, they shared nostalgic memories of their school days and the time they spent with friends during summer vacations in and around the town. Many of these individuals had studied together at this school before migrating to Africa and the U.K.

Conclusion:

Therefore, the study through the means of interviews and case studies shows the significant role of the Gujarati diasporic network, remittances and philanthropic contribution in the development process of Gujarat, especially through the case study of Nardipur and Dhamasana villages in Gandhinagar; and Sukhpar and Madhapar in Kachchh. The diaspora has helped sustain the development of Gujarat along with the government. The contribution of the diaspora community across various spheres of social, educational, health, and community development through philanthropy and remittances can be seen in the case studies and interviews selected for the paper. It also underscores the importance of governmental interaction with the Gujarati diaspora and need for policies that will help promote and improve the connection and relationship between the next generation of the diaspora and homeland.

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